

Headlines Demand Change, Mentality Remains Silent.

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ABSTRACT:

This research paper explores the importance of Women's Rights and globally peace keeping as an integral part of human rights and social development. This studies the evolution of thoughts of people from a male centered society towards an enlightened society through global laws and frameworks such as the (UDHR) Universal Declaration Of Human Rights and specialized Women Rights under Human Rights Laws and regulations mentioned under UN Charter.

But, the sole purpose of selecting this topic stems from the current social environment, where the mere existence of some Women-Centered Laws has sparked a Noise and discomfort among the well educated and responsible patriarch part of the society not only because this threaten them but because these laws actually challenge their long control over the society. This paper explores the point of technological advancement and freedom of profession choices rather than certain conventional choices decided for the women. The treaties bounded globally insist the peace making and peace keeping rules to be followed for the further development of human community likewise to promote sustainable development for the upcoming generations.

The reflection by the particular part of the society reveals the breakage of consevative and discriminatory thoughts and authority which only belongs to a certain community from the last many decades. Whereas women laws are never to over power but to provide the equality and freedom that belongs to everyone from the start because this world belongs also to women as much as it does to men. This paper is just for highlighting and restoring the thinking which claim women rights as just lawful rights not the privileges.

KEYWORDS:

Women Rights and gender diversification, Finanacial Freedom of Women, Women Leadership, Laws And Equality, Feminism.

INTRODUCTION:

As rightly said by sir Martin Luther King Jr. that, " Injustice anywhere is a threat to justice everywhere". Here by we talk about Human Rights. It is literally deals with basic rights of humans which helps in promoting the human values and keeps up the motivation to create a community and society.

Human rights are the essential rights which was inherent to all the human beings just because they are the part of human family. Human rights governs how every individual belongs to the society and with each other. Human rights are for everyone regardless of their nationality, language, religion or gender. They are universal, inalienable and equally important to everyone. Human rights initiated with the treaties, philosophical works and creative works which includes equality, dignity, protection, and respect for everyone. Human rights governed through the

foundational document (UDHR) Universal Declaration of Human Rights along with International Covenants and International Bills of Human Rights which is implemented and enforced by United Nations.

After World War II, Universal Declaration Of Human Rights was adopted by the UN General Assembly which serves as the common standard of human rights for all individuals and nations. It has inspired many international treaties which can help to achieve justice and social equality. It works as a road map to achieve freedom and equality with universal protection of every individual and everywhere. It is adopted as a answer to the abominable acts to ruin mankind which afterwards help to bring peace into the society. This formally consist of 30 Articles and are presently available in more than 500 languages. It shapes much of the national and global human rights and international laws and set a global standard for human rights. This is the foundational document for the human rights laws which promotes human dignity and diversity with the inspiring social and political change.

Before this, in the Ancient Era of human rights development the concepts which influence the evolvement of individual's position begins from the religious era which emphasize the concepts like equality and respect of every being regardless of his caste, sex, profession, religion, etc.

After World War II, a significant push for the recognition and protection of human rights and to discourage the inhumane character of authorities. The views over basic rights and duties of individuals have been shared from a long time which leads to it's development and evolvement. This development starts from 12th century through Magna Carta and it is continuing to evolve till date.

And in the Early Modern Era, Human Rights were developed efficiently and splendidly through Magna Carta during 12th century which establish certain rights including the right to fair trial and this provides an initial run to English Bill Of Rights which is based on the principles of Magna Carta. This was dealt by princely authorities. Then, the enlightenment era comes up with the idea of natural rights, international declarations and treaties with the influence of French declaration and US declaration.

Then, it's Modern Era where laws, treaties and conventions regularly influence the dynamic behaviors of humans and their needs for different kinds of rights. So, it is regularly changing with the importance of the hour. But, to maintain these rights and it's regulation is maintained by UN General Assembly and other different committees.

So, the different committees of United Nations (UN) are Drafting committee, UN General Assembly, Economic and Social Council, UN Human Rights Council, and some other bodies of UN which plays the sub roles to maintain and regulate broader human rights and framework of the declaration.

Human rights have been evolving since a long time now and it has favored to every being but as usual this society has always been cruel to women and it takes a lot of time as well as harsh cases for breaking those boundaries for them.

Establishment of UN Women agency and committee's like (United Nations Children's Fund) UNICEF, (United Nations Development Programme) UNDP, etc. helps to raise the funds for child care and women welfare. UN Women established because of a merger of UN Development Funds for women which was established in 1976. This was become operational

in 2011 which was operates under a governance structure and has an executive board representing different regions to complete the goals and standards formed by the members of UN Women Committee.

As well said, For the most of the history, Anonymous was always a woman! – “By Virginia Woolf”

Women rights are the entitlements and the freedoms which is already presented into the society as it is merely about recognizing and legally affirming those rights. These rights are not the new things but solely the acknowledgements of justice that was always overlooked and suppressed. Women rights includes equal rights for safety, education, equal salary and respect. Awareness for women rights is just for bringing the certain rights into picture which were already presented in the society. Bringing focus towards the rights of women so that society can divert towards development.

As rightly said by “APJ Abdul Kalam” that, “I firmly believe that the respect that it’s women enjoy tells us how developed a country is”. However, the creation of new laws can improve the society legally but can’t though changes it’s deeply routed biases or outdated thoughts. Laws can create a structural and strategic changes for development but real development and change in perspective comes from education, collective awareness and will of people who want to bring a change.

Women are always considered small, always belittled and every time they have to provide a proof for their passion, need or wishes. They are not responsible to change the society, they are the equal part of society so it’s their right to get everything or anything or any opportunity equally, unconditionally or without any boundations. As rightly said by Chanakya that, “A woman can be as soft, gentle and kind and as powerful and fierce which can called as epitome and essence of womanhood.

But, Feminism is neither a law we need nor any demand which is necessary to accomplish. It is a movement to seek equality of thoughts for everyone. It is not just to demand any particular gender attention but to create a change and to bring a change in our thoughts we all needed from a long time. Feminism not barely deals with women but it discusses the stories of dealings and essence of soft emotions which was presented inside everybody without the knowledge of gender. Usually, women are always considered soft that’s why people assumes and directed that the concept of feminism is solely belongs to women.

Women rights brings the attention and visibility over what should have already been guaranteed but Feminism brings out the courage and aims to provide a new shape to cultural thoughts and mindset. It talks about the stories of all those persons who seeks to live beyond the rigid boxes made by the society. Feminism explains that thoughts and freedom has no gender and this inspires to break the already made stereotypes and labelling by the society.

COMPREHENSIVE VIEW ON ARTICLES AND RIGHTS:

Indian constitution; law of the land is a very wide and exhaustive document which include all kinds of laws any citizen needs. And a series of protective rights available for women to deal with the crimes against women which help women to empower and promoting their well being

and freedom of equal participation in any public interest topic. These rights were necessary to upgrade their political, social and economic positions in the society.

These rights include Fundamental Rights, Maternity Rights, and Special Women Rights to support their freedoms, dignity and equality. Fundamental rights include Article 14, Article 15, Article 16, Article 19, Article 21, Article 25 and Article 243.

ARTICLE 14 which guarantees the equality for every person with equal treatment and equal laws for everyone. It includes that there is no denial for any women to use her rights and no one can really cease her to reach to court for the equal treatment of laws to conclude any inequality or wrongful act happened to her without any foundation of gender, race, religion. This has challenged the triple talaq system from Islamic laws which has created a great chaos.

As in this his case, it came to picture when one of the leading Air Lines of India restricted its female flight attendants by making several discriminatory policies like leading to marriage or getting pregnant during their term of job leads to the termination of their employment and if not this their employment automatically ends when they reach to the age of 35 years but on the other side male flight attendants not have to face this kind of discrimination. Here, Nargeesh Meerza filed a writ petition for the direct violations of fundamental rights of women like Article 14 and 15 which guarantees freedom and equality. On this matter, the apex court delivered the judgement where it removes the pregnancy clause but the marriage clause and early retirement policy did not get any attention which clearly defines certain stereotypes which are set in the work place.¹(*AIR 1981 SC 1829, Air India Vs. Nargeesh Meerza*).

ARTICLE 15 which states about prohibition of discrimination against any gender or race. This includes the right to equality and access to every public spot without any discrimination or biasness. This also includes mandatory reservation at some of the professions like panchayats, representation in government bodies, etc. This also includes right to education and admissions of women to educational institutions and helping them to overcome historical barriers of education.

ARTICLE 16 includes equality in opportunity they are given with during job hirings or at work places. And mandatory reservations are not because women can't achieve that position but because our society's learned men are not so learned that sometimes and some of them creates great havoc for women. This also advises about right to public employment and equal opportunities at work place with the right of equal and satisfied pay for women.

ARTICLE 19 guarantees the fundamental freedoms like freedom of speech and expression, or reside anywhere, or practice any profession, etc. Essential participation of women create a sense of clarity and break the unnecessary boundaries created for the sake of culture and outdated thoughts. This establishes a female point of view into the society which helps the new generation to understand and adapt the new change smartly. This explains about the freedom of thoughts

ARTICLE 21 guarantees right to life and personal freedom which helps in providing protection from work discrimination and provides safe work environment to women. It

¹ AIR 1981 SC 1829, Air India Vs. Nargeesh Meerza.

guarantees the right to marry and even to choose the person whom she wants to marry. It explains that neither any individual of the society nor society as the whole has any right to control any person of the society regardless of their gender. It's their own choice to take decisions in their own life whether it's marriage, children, work or divorce. But, Article 21 provides a vast and strong base for protection of their rights by ensuring their liberty with dignity and safeguards them from discrimination and violence or any kind of abuse.

ARTICLE 25 guarantees freedom of choosing any religion or right to practice any religion they have faith and believe in but what it protects the most when most of the religions or every religion has some or any boundaries which tends to discriminate women or clash their right to live freely and having a dignified life. It allows each and every person to enter any religious place to worship or to practice any religion they believe but the main role played by the judiciary here while it ensures that women are neither subjected to any discrimination or inequality nor they were objectified or compared like a mere object in the name of religion or cultural rules.

ARTICLE 243, specifically **Article 243D and 243T** highlights the importance of reserving seats for women in local governance and public offices. This article mandates as a significant step toward encouraging women's active involvement into the government institutions that draft and implement laws affecting their lives. By ensuring the inclusion of women's point of views in the policymaking process, it enables the development of more balanced and representative legislation. Such participation helps in challenging and reducing the discrimination women often face on the name of cultural norms and the long defined role of a "good woman" by the society. Ultimately, it contributes to the creation of fairer, more inclusive laws and secures the freedoms and rights that women rightfully deserve.

CRIMES AGAINST WOMEN: A BIRD'S EYE VIEW

Crime Against Women is such a vast concept to brief down, specifically it talks about women who has been victim of any abuse or violence because of any socio-cultural norms or our deep routed but outdated beliefs which adversely discriminate the women. These were punishable under Indian laws but this does not only shows the failure on personal or individual basis but it also shows how a whole society fails to protect and respect women. This shows how a society fails to maintain democracy even after having many and such a great laws to maintain equality and peace.

Some of the major crimes are domestic violence, harassment, assault, rapes, dowry death, human trafficking, forced prostitution, acid attacks, sexual harassment and verbal abuse at workplace, unequal pay for the same kind of work position compared to male, cyber crimes, witch-hunting which includes honor killings, and the number does not ends here there are uncountable crimes which are not listed but happens with a women to another based on different religions and it's beliefs. With this people does not stops here as artificial intelligence is probably for our help to complete our work on time effectively and efficiently with the best ever technology and to speed up the world towards more futuristic learnings but here people are too learned that they use artificial intelligence to create deep fake photos and videos to infringe the freedoms and rights of women. However, it is not about lack of laws but it is about the lack of understanding and sensibility in people.

The causes behind crimes against women are many but some of them are like delayed justice, male dominance, patriarchy and gender biasness, economic dependency of women and not let them work freely, victim blaming, etc. creates unnecessary boundaries for women. As said, there is no lack of laws but lack of people's understanding and enforcement or knowledge of the already made laws. It's no longer new to see candle marches being held to remind society of women's rights and freedoms after incidents of violence or abuse but the abuse continues as consistently as ever, showing that nothing can truly change in the condition of this society. These are some abuses or inequalities women has been facing for ages.

- 1. Female Foeticide:** The most illegal and inhumane abuse over a female starts before her birth, the acts to which society named Selective abortion which is generally a criminal act of foeticide and infanticide which is so common in Indian society. In India it is estimated that around 10 million female foetuses have been aborted in the last 20 years. The child sex ratio was 927 in 2001 which was declined to 914 in 2011. In spite of the fact that the Government of India have declared pre birth sex determination through the use of amniocentesis as unlawful, still Illicit termination of female foetuses by untrained nurses. All these have resulted in the escalation of maternal mortality rate. (Saryal, 2014)²
- 2. Dowry Deaths:** Asking for dowry or accepting dowry or giving of dowry is not a kind of respect you hold into the society but a kind of dead end of your respect into the society as well as inside yourself. Dowry is neither the right of the groom nor the duty of bride. But, we are forgetting something that this is the much learned Indian society who respects their customs over someone's death. And this is not something we conclude baselessly but the proper surveys and number of cases have been calculated into the government records. So, according to (NCRB) National Crime Records Bureau published that in 2019 almost 20,448 cases were registered for Dowry Harassment and Dowry Deaths and in 2020 almost 17,332 cases were registered for Dowry Harassment and Dowry Deaths. That's right the number of cases declined but even a single case is equally shameful for the society as the other hundreds or thousands of cases. (NCRB, 2022)³

Likewise this referred case is a pure example which advocates how sincerely the government is taking actions for the implementation of women rights in the society as well as it talks about women empowerment. This judgement delivers the official office notice declared by the petitioner for the protection of victims of domestic violence. It has also noticed that the cases of domestic violence has relatively increased during the lockdown period. This order was backed by the report submitted by the respondent over increasing numbers of domestic violence cases which was undertaken by NCT of Delhi and DCW under the provisions of Domestic Violence Act. Directions were given to suitably offers the duty to concerned District Magistrates/District Collectors and directed to provide protective gears and logistics support to all the personal working under this programme like helpline or call attendees of the victims. This decision was

² Sutapa Saryal Research Paper (2014).

³ NCRB Report of 2020.

taken over in three days and other amended measures implemented immediately.⁴ (*All India Council of Human Rights Liberties and Social Justice VS Union Of India And Others, 2020 SCC Online Del 537*).

- 3. Domestic Violence:** Domestic violence cannot be differentiated in categories as it can be through any way or in any circumstances regardless of how much time has been passed since marriage. Domestic violence can take many forms either emotional, physical, verbally abuse, stalking, taunts or threats, monetary or by any sense to affect the person's emotional or physical condition. So, according to (NCRB) National Crime Records Bureau published that in 2019 almost 1,25,487 cases were registered for Domestic Violence and in 2020 almost 1,11,995 cases were registered for Domestic Violence. Though numerous cases have been registered, domestic violence remains such a deeply rooted issue in Indian society that over time it has been normalized and treated as any other ordinary act. (NCRB, crime against women, 2022)⁵

This referred case backed the reason why females are referred as goddess or called shakti as same in this the mission shakti initiated which will work as an umbrella scheme for the implementation of Domestic Violence Act. Set up of one stop centres in every district which is always functioning and ready for the victim's help as for the 801 districts there should be 801 one stop centres and every assigned protection officer gets not less than 500 cases to solve on an average. And as per the judgement delivered by The Supreme Court that an action taken report in the form of an affidavit with the regard to the case to be filed within six weeks and the first meeting is to be convened as early as possible.⁶ (*We The Women Of India VS Union Of India And Others, 2023 SCC Online SC 905*)

- 4. Devadasis:** This concept has started primarily in South India and was started with a Bonafide intention of providing shelter to orphan women and girls who cannot care for themselves. This allows them to be often trained in classical dance and music forms and were certainly considered as married to the deity but eventually this took a misguided and faulty turn which headed towards prostitution and exploitation in the name of faith, values and deity. This degrades them towards the lowest level and forbid them to live a dignified life. After a long time, when it's abolition comes into the picture it was abolished a long back on papers or documents through statutes but the practice of Devadasi System still persists into the society for a long time. But, after the Devadasi's (Abolition) Act, which have completely prohibit such activities and any of the practices which works in contravention of this statute were counted as a criminal act and dealt under the rules of Bhartiya Nyaya Sahita (BNS) and Immoral Traffic (Prevention) Act. Number of developmental programs held for the victims to help them lead a dignified life and help them to take up income generation activities. (Affairs, 2015)⁷

⁴ All India Council of Human Rights Liberties and Social Justice VS Union Of India And Others, 2020 SCC Online Del 537.

⁵ NCRB Report of 2020.

⁶ We The Women Of India VS Union Of India And Others, 2023 SCC Online SC 905.

⁷ Abolition of Devadasi System Report, 2015.

5. **Rape:** This is the most common criminal act happens in Indian Society and a lot of strict laws were made and strict actions already been taken for the matters of assault and rapes but the question remains same as always is anything changed? The answer is remains the same as always which is no as somethings can never change in this society. So, the theory part on rape is not something we look into but when it comes to numbers it looks more vulnerable. So, asper the The Times Of India's Report on registration of Rape cases in 2023 was 1,99,954 cases which was increased in 2024 to 2,14,113 cases which is about a 7 % increase. (India, 2025)⁸ And these numbers are just about the cases which specifically registered but in certain conditions or in exceptional conditions victims are never guided about registration of a legal case or registration of FIR about the offence.

6. **Harassment At Work Place:** Mainly, this can be varied into two parts primarily physical assault or abuse and violation of someone's boundary through any physical act and secondarily verbal abuse or harassment through unnecessary or unwanted work rules or loopholes. Sexual or physical abuse is only one form of harassment that women have historically endured. However, when physical abuse is not possible, the harassment does not ceases there but instead subjected to verbal abuse in workplaces or are targeted through unjustified rules and legal loopholes embedded within the statutes like no paid maternity leave, less pay for the same position compared to males, priority preference to males, etc. But, some states were performing exceptionally well like Assam, Goa, Arunachal Pradesh, etc. but it will take time to cover all over the country. (Priya, 2025)⁹ As referenced in the given case of Air India Vs. Nargeesh Meerza that it takes a long time and alot of brutal cases to change the rules in statutes and to break the already made stereotypes or mindset of people.

WOMEN IN PRISONS: A BURIED ISSUE

Prisoners regardless of their gender, are fundamentally part of the human family and remain citizens of this country. Therefore, it is essential to ensure that they are granted all fundamental rights as well as any other rights applicable to their gender or specific circumstances. Article 21 of the Indian Constitution guarantees the right to life and protects the dignity of every individual including prisoners. This right covers protection against arbitrary detention, custodial violence, and sexual harassment, particularly for women. Additionally, Article 39A ensures the provision of free legal aid to all citizens, including those in custody and prisons. Under the Prisoners Act of 1894, women prisoners are entitled to certain specific protections which is an essential provision given noticing at the rising number of reported cases of custodial violence and harassment. It is also important to recognize that these statistics only represent the reported cases, while many others remain unreported and hidden from public view. (Khan, 2023)¹⁰

⁸ Times of India Article on increase in rape cases by 7% from 2023 to 2024. (2025 Publish).

⁹ Implementation of Maternity Benefit Act. (2025).

¹⁰ Rights of women prisoners in India, Research paper of International Journal of Research Publication and Reviews.

WOMEN IN MEDIA: SECRETLY VEILED

Journalism and reporting is an energetic, dynamic, and courageous profession in itself, yet it remains unsafe for women. Cases of sexual harassment in newsrooms and media houses continue to emerge and if neither this then threats to those who tries to speak truth, journalist being sent to prisons, financial burdens over journalists, physical violence or mob lynching cases, etc. The increasing privatization of media and its alignment with political interests often suppress the truth. These challenges not only endanger individual journalists but also undermine the very foundation of a free and independent press. Women journalist are subjected to what United Nations has called “ Double Attacks” they are threatened both online and offline. Indian women journalists such as Arfa Khanum, Rana Ayub, Neha Dixit, Bhasha Singh, Barkha Dutt, Sagarika Ghosh, Saba Naqvi, and Nidhi Razdan are all regularly subjected to vicious attacks on the social media platforms. As the report said in 2021 the World Press Freedom Index ranked India at 142 position out of 180 countries with a rise of 35% of women reporters sent to prisons, the position was declining by the solid 17 points being one of the biggest democratic country with the image one of the most dangerous country to live because of bizarre terror, weak laws, lengthy court procedures, killings and assaults. (Basu, 2022)¹¹ Usually, women in every profession face some form of abuse at their workplaces but it becomes truly alarming when such abuse enters a field that serves as one of the pillars of a democratic nation. It is especially dangerous when the ones assigned to ask the tough questions are instead forced to give answers to those powerful individuals who believe they run the country. Looking at this larger and threatening picture of women, The UNESCO made the action plan on the safety of women journalist and supported a publication written by a Egyptian journalist **ABEER SADDY** in 2017 named “**What if...Safety Handbook for Women Journalist**” on how to minimize the risk or first focus on self safety while covering sensitive and dangerous assignments or news and conduct capacity- building trainings for media managers. (UNWomen, 2020)¹²

ECONOMY AND WOMEN RIGHTS: THE EVIDENT CAUSE

India is a country with a vast population to support which include growing needs to maintain a reasonable standard of living. In such a context, it is neither practical nor fair that the responsibility of earning and financially sustaining a family falls solely on the shoulders of men. It raises a critical question that why is it considered acceptable to burden only men with the pressure of being the sole bread earners for the family while many educated and capable women despite possessing the skills and potential to earn a decent income, remain idle at home? Enabling and encouraging women to participate equally in the workforce is not just a matter of gender equality but a necessary step towards economic and social progress.

Asper National Family Health Survey (NFHS) survey conducted in 2019-2021 for calculating population data of India which shows that there were 1,020 women over every 1,000 males. (NFHS, 2022)¹³ It shows women conclude a greater number of population and it’s not new here to explain how population can create an effect to economic condition of the society and the

¹¹ Research Paper on Women Journalist Trolled And Targeted: India by Nupur Basu.

¹² Report by UN Women on safety of women journalist (2020).

¹³ NFHS Survey 5 Report (2022).

country. However, India is a developing economy which needs more people to be employed regardless of their gender to contribute positively in Indian economy to increase the standard of living and to match the International Standards of the global economy and development.

Although, India stands as the fourth-largest and one of the fastest-growing economies in the world, with a current GDP of \$4.19 trillion as reported by the World Economic Outlook (2025) (outlook, top economies of the world according to the GDP , 2025)¹⁴ a critical question arises why are individuals still struggling to find suitable employment or receive fair compensation in line with their qualifications? Many are compelled to accept low-paying jobs despite being overqualified, simply out of necessity. Further more, if we examine the trade imbalance, the import to export ratio presents an even more concerning picture. India continues to import a wide range of essential goods, contributing to rising inflation, an increase in the cost of essential commodities, and ultimately, a decline in the value of the Indian Rupee compared to other global currencies.

However, Government of India has implemented a series of visionary schemes and initiatives aimed at propelling the nation towards sustained economic growth and global leadership. From infrastructure development under the PM Gati Shakti National Master Plan to fostering innovation through initiatives like Startup India and the Production Linked Incentive Scheme, these reforms are transforming sectors such as manufacturing, digital economy, and financial inclusion. Collectively, they reflect India's commitment to building a resilient, self-reliant, and globally competitive economy. (broadcasting, 2025)¹⁵

On a positive note, this wave of development has contributed to increasing awareness around women's empowerment, particularly on digital platforms. The growing presence of such data through pie charts, reports, and statistics reflects a enhanced focus on women's progress and inclusion. However, the real concern lies in the gap between policy and it's implement. If these initiatives and strategies are genuinely empowering women, then why do we continue to observe significant disparities around ground level? Why do many women around us still face financial hardships and continue to feel unequal in everyday life? These questions highlight the urgent need to evaluate the actual impact of such measures beyond just numbers and digital narratives.

An analysis of the facts and figures report by UN Women reveals several shocking realities that remain largely unknown to the world like one in every ten women is living in extreme poverty and if this condition follows up till 2030 estimated 8 percent of women population will still lives on less than \$2.15 a day. Percentage of women is more who lacks for food freedom and are more likely food insecure as shown in the particular report, back in 2019 it was 1.7 percent but it was increased to 4 percent in 2021 who are insecure of getting food on daily basis. This number consist of mostly older women, and women with disabilities or who lives in remote areas. A serious gap persists in both awareness and education regarding menstrual hygiene, compounded by the inadequate availability of proper sanitation facilities not only in public areas but also in private establishments. It is deeply concerning that many restaurant owners impose conditions, such as requiring customers to make a purchase, simply to access washrooms. This practice underscores a broader issue which is the absence of inclusive and enforceable regulations that guarantee universal access to basic hygiene and sanitation, a

¹⁴ World Economic Outlook Report, 2025.

¹⁵ India Fastest-Growing Major Economy (Report by Ministry of Information and Broadcasting), 2025.

fundamental human right that should not be denied under any circumstance. And if we talk about the main reason behind all this cause is financial insecurity and lack of working culture for females as said in the particular report that usually women are less likely to have access to financial institutions or in easy words they are less likely to have a bank account. The bank account ownership has dropped in 2021 after COVID as in India the gap is about 6 percent than men whereas globally the gap sits for 4 percent compared to men. (Women, 2024)¹⁶

REFERRED CASES:

CASE 1. K. UMADEVI VS GOVERNMENT OF TAMIL NADU AND OTHERS (2025 SCC Online SC 1204):

This case advocates for the right to paid leaves and maternity benefit. In this case, the petitioner files appeal on the order given by divisional bench of the High Court. The petitioner was married to A. Suresh out of a wedlock in 2006 and have two living kids from that marriage. In 2012 she got the teaching position in a government school of Tamil Nadu and in 2017 her first marriage dissolved. In 2018, she married again and in 2021 she was expecting a child out of her second marriage. This was the timeline of this case's events. First order was given by the divisional bench of High Court while denying for any maternity benefit to the petitioner as she already has two living kids and as per the state maternity rules of Tamil Nadu does not allow maternity benefit for the third child. Then, the petitioner filed a appeal under Supreme Court. Here, the Court delivers a exceptional judgement where the Supreme Court grants maternity benefit to the petitioner under the Maternity Benefit Act, 1961 regardless of the fact that she already has two living kids but this kid is from her second marriage and regardless of any fact no women will be denied to grant the maternity benefits at her work place knowing the fact that she is pregnant but subjected to other conditions.¹⁷

ADVISORY AND MEASURES LAID BY GOVERNMENTAL INSTITUTIONS:

Certainly, we celebrate Women's Day once a year to acknowledge the rights granted to women, to reflect on the struggles endured in securing those rights, and to honour the rightful place women have always deserved in society. It is also a day dedicated to advocating for gender equality and eliminating discrimination. However, beyond this one day, the reality often remains unchanged crimes against women continue, and the daily challenges they face remains as usual. While the government has introduced various advisories and schemes aimed at empowering women across all regions of the country and ensuring equal rights and opportunities.

Advisory notice published by The Ministry Of Home Affairs on increasing the number of women in police force in all the states as as per the report only 5.33 percent which is 84,479 police officers are women against in the total strength 15.85 lakh police force in the whole country and presence of women in law enforcement agencies helps in heading all the procedures in such a systematic manner and also helps the police force to clean their image in

¹⁶ UN Women Report on Economic Empowerment, 2024.

¹⁷ Supreme Court Case, Citation: 2025 SCC Online SC 1204.

front of people which is a needful shift portrayed from a ruthless image towards the understanding one. Each police station should have at least 3 women sub-inspectors and 10 women police constables, so that a women help desk is manned round the clock. The objective should be to reach a level of thirty percent of strength of police force being comprised of women. (secretary, 2013)¹⁸

Official notice send by Ministry of Home Affairs to set up a central victim compensation fund and it's guidelines to be followed with the key objectives to support the existing victim scheme and back them by the governance of central government and encourage other states to effectively implement the victim compensation scheme and to reduce the disparity in compensation amount by different states for the victims of the similar crimes. (Affairs, Central Victim Compensation Scheme Guidelines , 2015)¹⁹

CONCLUSION:

Women rights are not just need of the hour but a pathway towards better future for us and equally for our future generation. Lack of implementation of laws and weak enforcement policies leads to migration of successful leaders and people in every domain from our country which is an alarming call in itself. Lacking in enforcing of women rights leads women to perform bitter actions by themselves and in result nowadays we are facing increasing criminal cases of murder, breaking marriages and financial frauds. Women rights majorly vary across different cultures and mindset of people but dignity of women never arise in question. Ancient women position in society blending with the new era rules and laws for attaining the equal position and dignity for women in the society. This reseach helps to motivate women to question on all the violence and abuse they endure because of the biased cultural teaching and advocates to question the prejudices made for them since their birth.

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